

Saponin of *Aesculus pinduana* Leaves

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AESCLUSUS Linn. is a genus of Hippocastanaceae family comprising 25 species of trees and shrubs distributed in Asia, Europe and America. *A. indica* and *A. pinduana* Wall. (syn. *A. assamica* Griff.) are the two species found in India. The 50% ethanolic extract of the fruits of *A. indica* is reported to possess diuretic activity¹ and the oil from the seeds is used in rheumatism. The fruits and bark of *A. hippocastanum* are useful in the treatment of fevers and as antiperiodic².

The reported diuretic activity and effect on cardiovascular system¹ of the ethanolic extract of *A. pinduana*, together with the medicinal uses and the interesting compounds reported³ from the genus prompted us to take up a detailed chemical investigation of the plant.

Experimental

Concentrated ethanolic extract of dried and powdered leaves (900 g) of *A. pinduana* was successively macerated with petroleum ether (4 × 250 ml), benzene (4 × 200 ml) and ethylacetate (4 × 200 ml) and the residual alcoholic extract was processed for saponin by the usual process to yield amorphous powder (12 g). The saponin (8 g) was acid hydrolysed and the sapogenins (5.3 g) thus obtained were subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (400 g) affording the following compounds.

The CHCl₃-MeOH (19:1) elution of the column gave an LB positive white compound (50 mg), m.p., 325-326°, (α)_D+29.5° (pyridine), M⁺, 490, analysed for C₂₀H₃₀O₆; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3370 (OH) and 1645 cm⁻¹ (double bond); MS m/e 490 (M⁺), 282, 264, 246, 215, 207, 197 and 189; penta acetate m.p. 152-155°. These spectral data suggested its identity as barringtogenol-C³ confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

Further elution of the column with the same solvent gave another LB positive white compound (150 mg), m.p. 262-265°, (α)_D+9.2°, M⁺, 572, C₂₅H₃₆O₆; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3390 (OH), 1695 (CO), 1640 and 1265 cm⁻¹; MS m/e 572 (3%, M⁺), 364(5), 282(3), 246(3.5), 215(16), 207(35), 197(5), 189(32) and 83(100). On acetylation with C₆H₅N-Ac₂O at room temperature it gave triacetyl derivative m.p., 280-282°, (α)_D+19.5°, C₄₁H₆₂O₉. On alkaline hydrolysis the compound gave barringtogenol-C, m.p. 325-326°, M⁺, 490 and tiglic acid (glc). The close resemblance of its m.p. and spectral data suggested its identity with 21-tiglate barringtogenol-C⁴.

The final elution of the column afforded LB positive white compound needles from MeOH, m.p. 241-245°; M⁺, 588, C₂₈H₃₆O₇; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3400 (OH), 1700 (CO) and 1645 cm⁻¹ (double bond); MS m/e 588 (M⁺), 364, 282, 246, 223, 215, 207, 197, 175 and 83 (base peak). On alkaline hydrolysis it gave protoaescigenin and tiglic acid. These data suggested its identity as protoaescigenin-21-tiglate⁵.

In the aqueous hydrolysate of the saponin, glucuronic acid, glucose and galactose were identified as sugars (co-pc).

The petroleum ether soluble fraction (15 g) of the alcoholic extract of *A. pinduana* leaves was chromatographed over silica gel (500 g). Elution of the column with *n*-hexane-benzene (3:1) afforded crystalline product, m.p. 84-85° which was identified as *n*-hentriacontanol by comparison with an authentic sample.

Further elution of the column with the same solvent gave an LB positive crystalline compound, m.p. 190-192°, (α)_D+90°, M⁺, 426, analysed for C₃₀H₅₀O; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3350 (OH), 825 and 813 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond), monoacetate, m.p. 232-235°. On the basis of spectral studies the compound was identified as β-amyrin and was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

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**O,O-Diethyl Phosphono/Phosphonothioyl
N,N-Dialkyldithiocarbamates**

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THE dithiocarbamate derivatives find their use as fungicides and pesticides¹. Besides their biological significance, the dithiocarbamate ligands possess a structural importance too. They can form either monodentate or bidentate metal complexes. In earlier communications²⁻⁵ we reported a number of organometallic compounds of N,N-dialkyl and N,N-alkylcyclohexyl dithiocarbamates. In all these compounds, the dithiocarbamate ligands are bidentate. In continuation, we report the study of a set

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